

its conversion to tetrahydropiperlongumic acid², $C_{17}H_{25}NO_6$, m.p. 114° by catalytic hydrogenation.

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Studies on Heterocyclic Compounds : Part I.

Synthesis of 3-amino-2-sub-Imidazo(1,2-a)-pyridines

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BRISTOW *et al*¹ prepared 2-pyridyl amino acetonitrile in search for antihistaminic properties and suggested that the compounds behaved as amines by rearrangement rather than as nitriles. Ohta *et al*² also

prepared the α -(2-pyridyl amino)-sub acetonitriles and used them for the preparation of mesoionic compounds. Almirante *et al*³ also synthesised nitrogen containing derivatives of imidazo(1,2-1)-pyridine for the study of their pharmacological properties.

In continuation of our studies on ($\pm$)-aminoacetonitriles⁴, we have prepared ($\pm$)-pyridyl aminoacetonitriles which rearrange into 3-amino-2-imidazo(1,2-a)-pyridines. The aldehyde bisulphite addition product

3-Amino-2-sub-imidazo (1,2-a)-pyridines

was reacted with 2-aminopyridine followed by aqueous potassium cyanide to get the imidazo(1,2-a)-pyridines (Table 1). The ir spectrum of 3-amino-2-phenyl-imidazo(1,2-a)-pyridine supported the amine structure confirming the view of Bristow *et al*^(1,00,011). Another supporting evidence has been obtained by condensing 3-amino-2-phenyl-imidazo(1,2-a)-pyridine with different aldehydes when anils were obtained (Table 2).

The ir spectrum of 3-amino-2-phenyl-imidazo(1,2-a)-pyridine recorded on Backman IR 5 spectrophotometer on KBr pellet shows characteristic aminofrequencies instead of any absorption between 2260-2240 cm^{-1} (the $-C\equiv N$ -region). Most of the compounds showed antibacterial activity in preliminary screening.

TABLE 1

3-AMINO-2-SUB-IMIDAZO (1, 2-A)-PYRIDINES

No.	R	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	% N	
				Found	Required
1.	H	C_7H_7N	124	31.70	31.57
2.	CH_3	C_8H_9N	134	28.67	28.57
3.	C_6H_5	$C_{12}H_{11}N$	210	20.20	20.09
4.	2-Cl- C_6H_4	$C_{12}H_{10}ClN$	152	17.42	17.24
5.	2-OH- C_6H_4	$C_{12}H_{11}N_2O$	122	18.42	18.66
6.	2-OH-5-Br- C_6H_3	$C_{12}H_{10}BrN_2O$	220	13.61	13.81
7.	4-OH- C_6H_4	$C_{12}H_{11}N_2O$	210 (d)	16.72	16.66
8.	C_6H_5O	$C_{11}H_9N_2O$	175 (d)	20.20	21.11
9.	4- CH_3O - C_6H_4	$C_{14}H_{13}N_2O$	131	17.47	17.57
10.	4-OH-3- OCH_3 - C_6H_3	$C_{14}H_{13}N_2O_2$	222	16.32	16.47
11.	2- OCH_3 -5-Br- C_6H_3	$C_{14}H_{12}BrN_2O$	210	13.42	13.20
12.	3,4- CH_2O_2 - C_6H_3	$C_{14}H_{11}N_2O_2$	255 (d)	16.82	16.60
13.	4- $CH_3C_6H_4$	$C_{14}H_{13}N_2$	252	18.92	18.83

TABLE 2

3-ARYLIDINE AMINO-2-PHENYL-IMIDAZO (1, 2-A)-PYRIDINES

No.	R	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	% N	
				Found	Required
1.	C_6H_5	$C_{20}H_{15}N_3$	137	14.20	14.14
2.	2-OH- C_6H_4	$C_{20}H_{15}N_3O$	245	13.60	13.41
3.	4-OH- C_6H_4	$C_{20}H_{15}N_3O$	160	13.23	13.41
4.	2-OH-5-Br- C_6H_3	$C_{20}H_{14}BrN_3O$	182	10.62	10.71
5.	4- NO_2 - C_6H_4	$C_{20}H_{14}N_4O_2$	205	16.52	16.37
6.	3- NO_2 - C_6H_4	$C_{20}H_{14}N_4O_2$	149	16.10	16.37
7.	C_6H_5O	$C_{18}H_{13}N_3O$	139	14.82	14.63
8.	4-OH-3- CH_3O - C_6H_3	$C_{21}H_{17}N_3O_2$	208	12.12	12.24

Experimental

3-Amino-2-sub-imtdazo (1, 2-a)-pyridines :

Aldehyde bisulphite addition product (0.1 M) was added to 2-aminopyridine (0.1 M, 9.4 g) in water (60 ml) and heated on a waterbath for 2 hrs, filtered, cooled (30°), KCN (0.1 M, 6.5 g) in water added and stirred for 5 hrs. It was extracted with CHCl₃ (3 × 50 ml), CHCl₃ extract dried over Na₂SO₄ and the solvent distilled off at reduced pressure. The residue was treated with petroleum ether and crystallised from ethanol (95%) (Table 1).

Preparation of Schiff bases :

3-Amino-2-phenyl-imidazo (1, 2-a)-pyridine and aldehydes in equimolar proportion were refluxed in alcohol for 2 hrs. The anils separated on cooling. They were filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol (95%) (Table 2).

3-Arylidine amino-2-phenyl-imidazo (1, 2-a)-pyridines

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On Glucosyl Thioureides : Preparation of Certain S-Tetra-O-Acetyl-D-Glucopyranosyl Aryl Isothiocarbamides

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THE pharmacological and biochemical aspects of alkyl/aryl ureides, -thioureides and -guanidines have been very extensively investigated and many compounds of this series have been described in the literature¹. They have been found to possess marked biological activities and are used as bacteriostatic agents and diuretic, analgesic, antithyroid drugs. A very few thioglucosides of thiocarbamides are reported to date¹. In the present communication seven S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides have been reported. These were prepared by the interaction of tetra-O-

acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl bromide (I) and aryl thiocarbamides (II).

(I)

Ac=Acetyl

Isopropanolic solution of tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl bromide (0.04 M, 16 g in 25 ml) was mixed with a suspension of phenyl thiocarbamide (0.04 M, 6 g in 25 ml isopropanol) and the mixture after shaking for about ten mins was warmed over a hot water bath at 70° until a clear solution was obtained. The clear solution was then kept at room temperature for 18 hrs. It was mixed with water when a small quantity of semi solid was obtained. The aqueous layer was separated. This aqueous solution was acidic and non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. When treated with aqueous picric acid, it afforded a picrate, m.p. 155°. All these clearly indicated the presence of S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl phenyl isothiocarbamide hydrobromide in aqueous solution.

The aqueous solution when made basic with NH₄OH, afforded a sticky mass which solidified on standing for several hours and crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 138°. It gave Molisch test and was non-desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. It gave a picrate, m.p. 155°, when warm ethanolic solution of it was treated with ethanolic picric acid. It's specific rotation was $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 5.86^\circ$ (C, 2.2 in CHCl₃). The ir spectrum clearly indicated the presence of ν_{NH} 3410 cm⁻¹, $\nu_{C=O}$ 1720 cm⁻¹, $\nu_{C=N}$ 1650 cm⁻¹ and ν_{C-S} 750 cm⁻¹ bands^{4,5}. All these clearly indicated the product as S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl phenyl isothiocarbamides (IIIa).

When the interaction of tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl bromide was extended to other aryl thiocarbamides the related S-tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl aryl isothiocarbamides (IIIb-IIIg) were isolated. All these products afforded picrates and have been listed in Table 1.

where, R=(a) Phenyl, (b) o-Tolyl, (c) m-Tolyl, (d) p-Tolyl, (e) o-Cl-Phenyl, (f) m-Cl-Phenyl and (g) p-Cl-Phenyl

TAG=Tetra-O-acetyl-D-glucopyranosyl.